

Synthesis of Newer 3-Cyclohexyl-1-alkylselenoureas and 2-(*N*-Nitrosocyclohexylamino)-2-selenazoline

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The clinically useful 1-(2-chloroethyl)-3-cyclohexyl-1-nitrosourea (CCNU) is effective in the treatment of brain tumor and other malignant diseases¹. Since the selenium compounds are more liquid soluble² than the corresponding oxygen and sulphur compounds, the synthesis of selected 3-cyclohexyl-1-alkylselenoureas and other related reactions have been carried out in an attempt to synthesise better drugs for brain tumors.

The reaction of cyclohexyl isoselenocyanate (1) with alkylamines (2) gave 3-cyclohexyl-1-alkylselenoureas (3) in 80–90% yield. When 1 was treated with 2-chloroethylamine (2c) as the alkylamine instead of 1-(2-chloroethyl)-3-cyclohexylselenourea (3c), 2-(cyclohexylamino)-2-selenazoline hydrochloride (7) was formed (Scheme 1). The cyclisation of 3-cyclohexyl-1-(2-hydroxyethyl)selenourea (3d) under acidic conditions also gave 7 in good yield.

The nitrosation of the selenoureas were carried out at different concentrations of HCl with NaNO₂ and in all the cases corresponding ureas (4) and with excess of NaNO₂ corresponding nitrosourea were formed. Dilute (~0.07 N)

acidic conditions were selected so as to favour the formation of unprotonated nitrous acid and N₂O₃⁴. Since these species may be harder acids⁵ than the nitrosonium ion or its derivatives, they were anticipated to favour electrophilic attack at the harder nitrogen of selenoureas rather than at the competing soft selenium atom. In the event, when a suspension of selenoureas and NaNO₂ in dichloromethane at -10° was treated with 1 equiv. of dilute HCl (0.07 N), a yellow colour developed which slowly disappeared by the precipitation of red selenium.

Since 2-cyclohexylamino-3-nitrosooxazolidine is the major aqueous decomposition product of CCNU⁶, the nitrosation reaction of 2-cyclohexylamino-2-selenazoline (8) was carried out. Owing to the acid liability of selenazolines, the nitrosation of 8 was carried out with *n*-butyl nitrite in the presence of sodium methoxide^{6b,7} in ether, to form 2-(*N*-nitrosocyclohexylamino)-2-selenazoline (8) as the major product and the isolation of 2-cyclohexylamino-3-nitrososelenazoline (9) could not be achieved (Scheme 1). In the ¹H nmr spectrum, the downfield shift of H-1' proton of cyclohexyl ring indicates the presence of the nitroso group at the exocyclic nitrogen atom. This is further confirmed by the upfield shift in the position of the C-1, C-2' and C-6' carbon atoms of 9 in the ¹³C nmr⁸ as compared to their corresponding position in selenazoline 8.

Experimental

¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra were recorded on a Jeol FX200 spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as internal standard and ir spectra on a Shimadzu 435 spectrometer. M.p.s. were measured on a Thomas Hoover Unimelt apparatus and are uncorrected.

3-Cyclohexyl-1-alkylselenourea (3): To a stirred solution of cyclohexyl isoselenocyanate (1: 10 mmol) in petroleum ether (100 ml), alkylamine (12 mmol) in ether (25 ml) was added dropwise and the stirring was continued overnight, and the resulting solid crystallised. **3-Cyclohexyl-1-methylselenourea (3a; 92%)**, m.p. 174–75° (CHCl₃) (Found: C, 44.09; H, 6.43. C₆H₁₆N₂Se requires: C, 44.25; H 6.41%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 200, 2 900, 1 555, 1 498, 1 265, 1 230 cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-d₆) 1.00–2.00 (10H, m, CH₂), 3.00 (3H, br, CH₃), 4.18 (1H, br, H-1), 7.60 (2H, br, NH). **3-Cyclohexyl-1-ethylselenourea (3b; 86%)**, m.p. 125° (CHCl₃) (Found: C, 47.10; H, 6.96. C₉H₁₈N₂Se requires:

C, 46.96; H, 7.00%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 200, 2 895, 1 555, 1 490, 1 450, 1 265, 1 165, 970 and 610 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.08–22.16 (10H, m, CH_2), 1.28 (3H, t, CH_3), 4.00 (2H, br, CH_2), 6.36 (2H, br, NH). 3-Cyclohexyl-1-(2-hydroxyethyl)selenourea (3d; 84%), m.p. 120° (MeOH-ether) (Found : C, 43.78; H, 6.47. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{OSe}$ requires : C, 43.90; H, 6.55%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 250, 2 900, 2 850, 1 540, 1 505, 1 425, 1 330, 1 285, 1 225, 1 195, 1 110, 1 050, 905, 880, 860 and 610 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.10–2.10 (10H, m, CH_2), 3.60 (4H, br, $2\times\text{CH}_3$), 4.04 (1H, br, H-1'), 5.94 (1H, br, OH), 8.9 (2H, br, NH).

2-Cyclohexylamino-2-selenazoline (8) : Cyclohexyl isoselenocyanate was treated with 2-chloroethylamine as above. The resulting solid was dried to get 2-cyclohexylamino-2-selendazoline hydrochloride (7). An ethereal suspension of 7 was basified with aqueous NaOH and extracted with ether. Removal of ether gave 2-cyclohexylamino-2-selenazoline (8; 90%). 8 was also prepared by refluxing 3-cyclohexyl-1-(2-hydroxyethyl)selenourea (0.8 g, 3 mmol) in formic acid (20 ml; 85%) for 1 h. Excess formic acid was then removed under reduced pressure and the resulting residue was basified with dilute NaOH. The product was washed with cold water and crystallised from chloroform, (92%), m.p. 170° (Found : C, 46.80; H, 7.50; N, 11.90. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{Se}$ requires : C, 46.75; H, 7.41; N, 12.11%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 150, 2 900, 2 850, 1 600, 1 530, 1 440, 1 315, 1 125, 1 090, 1 016, 920, 880, 590 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.0–2.20 (10H, m, CH_2), 3.40 (2H, t, Se- CH_2), 3.60 (2H, br, H-1' and NH), 3.95 (2H, t, N- CH_2); $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (CDCl_3) 24.87 (C-3' and C-5'), 25.66 (C-4), 33.75 (C-2' and C-6'), 55.10 (C-1'), 61.72 (C-5), 156.28 (C-2).

2-(N-Nitrosocyclohexylamino)-2-selenazoline (9) : n-Butyl nitrite (6.18 g, 60 mmol) was added dropwise to a suspension of 8 (1.15 g, 5 mmol) and sodium methoxide (0.32 g, 6 mmol) in dry ether (150 ml) at 0–5° during 1 h and the mixture was stirred for 16 h room temperature. The resulting solid was then filtered off and the filtrate

was concentrated. The residue was chromatographed on alumina (neutral) using petroleum ether as eluent to give 9 (56%, 0.73 g), m. p. 54–55° Found : C, 41.08; H, 5.72; N, 16.62. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{OSe}$ requires : C, 41.54; H, 5.81; N, 16.15%); ν_{\max} (film) 2 900, 2 850, 1 630, 1 485, 1 445, 1 340, 1 280, 1 155, 1 070, 920, 895, 820, 740 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 0.80–2.20 (10H, m, CH_2), 3.42 (2H, t, Se- CH_2), 4.39 (2H, t, N- CH_2), 5.44 (1H, m, H-1'); $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (CDCl_3) 26.20 (C-4'), 27.12 (C-3' and C-5'), 29.6 (C-2' and C-6'), 29.90 (C-4'), 54.54 (C-1'), 62.05 (C-5), 156.6 (C-2).

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